

Revival of classic Affixes in Spanish through English

ISABEL DE LA CRUZ-CABANILLAS

CRISTINA TEJEDOR-MARTÍNEZ

Universidad de ALCALÁ

Abstract

The increasing impact of English upon Spanish pervades not only its lexicon, but also its morphology. The goal of the article is to see if the revival of several affixes in Spanish is likely due to English influence. These affixes, available in the classic languages, have mainly come down to us through Latin, even though some of them are Greek in origin. This article focuses on the revival of several of these classic affixes that are highly productive in Present-Day Spanish. The data have been retrieved from a corpus containing twenty-first-century written texts in European Spanish and have been compared to information from other corpora and several lexicographic works both in English and Spanish. The resources that are mentioned enable the chronological order of the recording of the items to be traced. This timeline will help to establish the influence of the English lexical units in the coinage of their Spanish counterparts.

Keywords: Derivative inflection, English influence, Anglicisms, European Spanish, specialised languages

1. Introduction

Much has been written recently on the presence of English as a global language in the lexicon of the languages of Western Europe (Görlach 2002; Fischer and Pulaczewska 2008; Furiassi, Pulcini and Rodríguez González 2012). The increasing influence of English upon the European Spanish word-stock is evidenced through borrowings (*ranking*), calques (*ratón*) and hybrid combinations (*hockey sobre hielo*). Furthermore, its impact pervades not only the Spanish lexicon, but also its morphology, syntax, semantics and phraseology (Gómez-Capuz 2004:42-63 and 2005:36-56).

We follow Furiassi, Pulcini and Rodríguez-González (2012:5), who refer to Anglicisms “as an umbrella label for any sign of interference – phonological, morphological, syntactic and phraseological (but also semantic, pragmatic, stylistic and cultural) – which may be ascribed to the influence of the English language”. On this occasion, we concentrate on the interference of the English language in derivation by affixation in Spanish.

According to Plag (2003:74), “perhaps the most obvious of the usage-based factors influencing productivity is fashion. The rise and fall of affixes like *mega-*, *giga-*, *mini-* or *-nik* is an example of the result of extra-linguistic developments in society which make certain words or morphological elements desirable to use”. Although this claim is made in the context of English word formation processes, it is absolutely applicable to European Spanish. Using English in Spain is viewed as a sign of identity, a mark of belonging to an elite that *masters* a fashionable

language (Estornell-Pons 2012:100; Walsh 2017:368). Thus, even though there is often a native linguistic device to replicate the foreign pattern, the borrowing form is sometimes preferred. The reason behind the use of some affixed creations can be even more subtle, such as when the affix is available in the language and its use is not considered foreign. Subsequently, Spanish speakers feel they are natural to their language. This is the case of several classic affixes, such as *anti-*, *hiper-*, *super-*, *eco-* and *micro-*, the preference for which on part of Spanish speakers is likely due to English influence. Our hypothesis is that several classic affixes, which have been available in the language since its early stages,¹ have recently become highly productive in Spanish due to the influence of English. This idea was already explored by several scholars, such as Gómez-Capuz (2004, 2005) and Estornell-Pons (2012). The present article is not meant to be a comprehensive study on all Spanish affixes, as it is based on the examples extracted from the corpus compiled by the authors. Accordingly, only those items found in the corpus, which contain similar prefixes or prefixoids to English terms, have been selected.

2. Methodology

To carry out the research, the data have been retrieved from a corpus and an associated database, known as ANGLICOR,² which the authors have been compiling since 2003. The corpus is a collection of printed and online texts from magazines, brochures, academic journals, leaflets, manuals and websites written in European Spanish in the twenty-first century. The corpus is made up of several subcorpora, the main topics of which are: computers, medicine and health, science and technology, fashion, beauty and tourism.³ Firstly, the subcorpus on computers includes manuals on the history of the Internet and computer magazines, such as *PC World* and *PC Actual*, among others. Secondly, the medicine and healthcare subcorpus contains specialized publications aimed at physicians, such as *Jano*, and other magazines whose target audience is the public. Thirdly, the science and technology subcorpus comprehends general magazines on the topic, such as *Quo*. Recently, a subcorpus on fashion and beauty has been incorporated with magazines like *Cosmopolitan*, *Vanity Fair*, *Vogue* or *Elle*, and leaflets from cosmetic products, like *SkinClinic*, *Germaine de Capuccini* or *Farma Dorsch*. Finally, the largest subcorpus is made up of several printed and online sources dealing with the field of tourism. The latter is a compilation of texts from leaflets, academic journals, websites, brochures from tourism agencies, magazines distributed on planes and trains, and tourism magazines; namely, *Outdoor*, *Turismo & Aventura*, *Viajeros*, *Grandes Espacios*, *Aire Libre* and *Top Viajes*.

¹ Examples, such as *anticlerical*, *hipercrítico*, *minifundio*, *multiforme* or *superponer*, are not related to the influence of English, since they have been documented in the history of the Spanish language for a long time.

² The database ANGLICOR, which stands for *Anglicisms Corpus* (<https://anglicor.web.uah.es>) is part of the research carried out by the group *Linguistic Analysis (Análisis Lingüístico)*.

³ For further details on the sources for the tourism subcorpus, see De la Cruz-Cabanillas and Tejedor-Martínez (2019).

Lorenzo (1996:27) admits that researchers, such as Alfaro, Pratt and himself, did not have enough recorded data when dealing with the study of the English influence in the Spanish language. However, corpus linguistics is a powerful methodology that provides real and current examples to carry out this work. Therefore, a selection of lexical units coined by using prefixes and prefixoids was extracted from our corpus in order to analyse the English influence on the derivational processes in European Spanish.

The lexical units that were extracted from the corpus have been compared across several sources. The lexicographical sources and electronic databanks serve to check whether the item was recorded in English prior to Spanish. If this is the case, a possible influence of English on the Spanish appearance of the word can be claimed.

We have consulted the following sources to carry out the study. Three editions of the general Spanish monolingual dictionary, the *Diccionario de la lengua española* (henceforth DLE)⁴ published by the *Real Academia Española* (RAE, Royal Academy of the Spanish Language) and *Asociación de Academias de la Lengua Española* (ASALE, Society of Academies of the Spanish Language). The possible English equivalents of these items have been checked in the *Oxford English Dictionary* (henceforth OED) to see if we could set up the timeline when these specific words started being used in both languages. Occasionally, the *Diccionario histórico de la lengua española* (*Historical Dictionary of the Spanish language*, henceforth DHLE, also published by RAE), formerly *Nuevo diccionario histórico del español* (*New Historical Dictionary of Spanish*) was also consulted, but the results were not conclusive at all, given the fact that most words do not appear in this specific source.

Notwithstanding, unlike previous analyses, which are based exclusively on lexicographic works (e.g. Bull 1965; Smead 2000; Morin 2010), our study does not only use dictionary sources, but relies on several corpora in Spanish and in English to see if we could establish the occurrence of specific words in both languages. Thus, the consultation of corpora will provide an up-to-date overview of the vernacular use of the lexical items. Therefore, we considered that the *Corpus de Referencia del Español Actual* (henceforth CREA) and the *Corpus Diacrónico del Español* (henceforth CORDE), by the *Real Academia Española*, would be the best sources to check for this research. The reason behind the choice is that a word can be incorporated in the DLE although it is not registered in the CREA and CORDE and, likewise, it can be recorded in the CREA and CORDE and not in the DLE. Therefore, the use of corpora supplies further the information registered in the lexicographical sources in Spanish. Regarding the English language, the *British National Corpus* (henceforth BNC) has been checked, as it is an acknowledged corpus of British English created by Oxford University Press. It can complement the information registered in the OED, because both are reliable sources that

⁴ The paper versions of the DLE published in 1992 and 2001, and the ongoing online version (2022) have been consulted (<https://dle.rae.es>).

provide information about the vocabulary of the English language. These two sources supplement each other, since the BNC provides synchronic data and the OED includes information on previous periods of the language. In the case of the Spanish language, the DLE does not offer historical details, which explains the incorporation of the CORDE corpus.

Finally, we have also consulted the FundéuRAE, which is a non-profit institution, created in 2005 and promoted by the RAE and the EFE Agency (Agencia EFE) whose main objective is to promote the proper use of the Spanish language. The combination of lexicographic sources and corpora will serve to offer the most comprehensive information available on European Spanish word-stock, as well as to test our hypothesis and that there is a potential influence of the English language upon European Spanish in terms of lexical morphology.

3. Analysis and discussion

Before proceeding to the analysis of each item, it is worth noticing that out of the one hundred and eight lexical units analysed (eighty-five derivatives by prefixation and twenty-three including prefixoids), thirty-six are recorded in the latest version of the DLE, although they were not included in previous versions. This fact evidences that these lexical units have been used in Spanish during the most recent decades. Nevertheless, it should be pointed out that a great number of the items studied are not recorded in any version of this dictionary, as can be checked in Table 1. In fact, the dictionary policy indicates that the possibilities for the formation of derived words are very broad, which implies not all possible combinations are included in the dictionary. All in all, in the annual updates of the dictionary new derived words are incorporated even though they could be easily deduced by consulting the meaning of the affixes. Their inclusion is due to the fact that new words or meanings whose use is frequent are considered to add new entries on a regular basis. One of the sources used by the RAE and ASALE is the CREA corpus. Therefore, the inclusion of these words in the CREA indicates that these derivatives could be regarded as elements of the Spanish language and could be incorporated in the dictionary at some point.

Table 1. Elements not recorded in the three versions of the DLE

anti-colesterol	interconectividad	miniserie	superintensivo
anti-edad	maxi falda	minitallas	superperfeccionista
anti-empañamiento	maxianillo	minivacaciones	superpopular
antiestresante	maxi-brazaletes	minivestidos	superrentable
anti-polución	maxigargantilla	multiactividad	supertodoterreno
cibercrimen	maxijersey	multiaventura	superyate
ciberregalo	maxijoyas	multifacético	ultracorrector
detoxificación	maxiplataformas	multisectorial	ultradelgado
detoxificador	microcirculación	superalimento	ultradiseño
detoxificante	micro-inyecciones	superaprendizaje	ultra-dosificado
detoxificar	microrelieve	superbrillante	ultralujo
distrés	minicámara	superelegante	ultramaratón
ecoagroturismo	minicolección	superfeliz	ultrarreparador
eco-sostenible	minilibro	superguay	ultrarresistente

3.1 Prefixes

Anti- is a polysemous prefix that can express two different but related notions. On the one hand, it can have the value of ‘against, opposing’ and has traditionally been attached to adjective bases with this meaning. Thus, it is frequently found in scientific vocabulary in *antialérgico*, *antibacteriano*, *anticelulítico*, *antihistamínico* (Gutiérrez-Rodilla 1998:115) or in our corpus *antiestresante*, as in “En la dieta no deben faltar alimentos antiestresantes como el plátano” (*Saber Vivir* 2008:89).

On the other hand, it can mean ‘protection against something’. According to Lorenzo (1996:115), due to the influence of the English language, this prefix now appears in nouns: either because the adjective has shifted its word category, such as *antidepresivo* (Capanaga 2002:71), or just because it is used in combination with noun bases to create neologisms, like *antiarrugas*, *antiedad*, *antipolución*, *antivirus*, as can be seen in the following examples from the cosmetic leaflets by the brand *Germaine de Capuccini*:

(1) *Anti-edad*: activa la oxigenación de la piel (*Germaine de Capuccini*, June 2017).

(2) Activo neutralizador *anti-polución*⁵ de origen biotecnológico que aporta un alto nivel de protección frente a los efectos de la contaminación medioambiental (*Germaine de Capuccini*, June 2017).

Some of the new creations sound strange to Spanish speakers, such as *anti-empañamiento* that appears on Adventure tourism webpages:

(3) Como el mono de camuflaje, el protector de cuello, el chaleco, el cinturón, los guantes, las rodilleras, la máscara *anti-empañamiento*, el casco, walkie-talkies para que podamos estar comunicados con los nuestros en todo momento (Turismoactivo.net).

⁵ To help readers to follow the examples, the analysed words have been highlighted in italics, even if they are not printed with such a mark in the original source.

When **anti-** is used with a noun, it sometimes competes with the English pattern *no + noun*: we can find *antiestrés*, but also *no-stress*, as seen in:

(4) Contiene Té Verde, el cual proporciona un excepcional efecto calmante y *antiestrés* (*Natura Bissé*, June 2017).

(5) Aplicar **Crema hidratante *no-stress*** sobre la piel limpia y renovada de rostro, cuello y escote (*Germaine de Capuccini*, June 2017).

Finally, the prefix of negation, *anti-*, is an example of productivity, which “has evolved semantically towards the concept of ‘protection’ or ‘defense’” (Lang 1990:171), as is the case in the examples shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Prefix *anti-* in dictionaries and corpora

Spanish item	DLE 1992	DLE 2001	DLE online	CORDE	CREA	English item	OED	BNC
antialérgico	X	✓	✓	X	✓1997	anti-allergic	X	✓1985
antiarrugas	X	X	✓	X	✓1995	anti-wrinkle	X	✓1960
antibacteriano	X	✓	✓	X	✓1988	anti-bacterial	✓1897	✓1985
anti-colesterol	X	X	X	X	✓1994 no hyphen	anti-cholesterol	X	X
antidepresivo	X	✓	✓	X	✓1987	anti-depressant	✓1962	✓1975
anti-edad	X	X	X	X	✓2001 no hyphen	anti-ageing	X	✓1985
anti-empañamiento	X	X	X	X	X	anti-fog	X	✓1985
antiestrés	X	X	✓	X	✓1986	anti-stress	X	✓1985
antiestresante	X	X	X	X	X	anti-stressing	X	X
antihistamínico	X	✓	✓	✓1969	✓1986	anti-histamine	✓1933	✓1985
anti-polución	X	X	X	X	✓1980 no hyphen	anti-pollution	✓1966	✓1985
antivirus	X	✓	✓	X	✓1993	anti-virus	✓1914	✓1960

Regarding the lexical units shown in Table 2, there has been an increase in the number of items included in the DLE from the first paper version, where not a single entry for the elements shown above is registered, to the second paper version, containing five words (*antialérgico*, *antibacteriano*, *antidepresivo*, *antihistamínico*, *antivirus*), and to the current online version, which incorporates *antiarrugas* and *antiestrés* to the previous list. When checking the CREA and CORDE corpora, ten elements are found in the former and only one in the latter (*antihistamínico*).

As for their English counterparts, ten are recorded in the BNC and five in the OED. Most derivatives have been attested firstly in the English language. The two items not documented in the English sources are *anti-cholesterol* and *anti-stressing*. Regarding the derivative word, *anti-colesterol*, the influence of the English language is reflected in the orthographical pattern. This same pattern appears in *anti-edad*, *anti-empañamiento* and *anti-polución*. The Royal Academy of the Spanish Language indicates that “it is not considered orthographically correct when the prefix is joined to its base by a hyphen (**anti-mafia*, **anti-cancerígeno*) or

separated from it by a blank space (*anti mafia, anti cancerígeno*)" (RAE 2010:535),⁶ having been copied from the English language and thus reflects its influence in the formation of these items.

Dis- versus des-/de-

In medicine, formations containing *dis-* that come from English nouns are found. A clear example is *distrés*, which is not recorded in the online version of the DLE, but documented in the OED as *distress* since 1297 with the meaning: "The sore pressure or strain of adversity, trouble, sickness, pain, or sorrow; anguish or affliction affecting the body, spirit, or community". The examples from our corpus are:

- (6) Con un importante *distrés* psicológico asociado (*Jano*, October 2008).
- (7) Durante más de 2 meses después de la desaparición de una infección activa ya tenían antes esa fatiga o *distrés* (*Jano*, October 2008).

Despite these specialised nouns containing *dis-*, *des-* is the most widely used prefix for negation in Spanish due to its versatility to be combined with different bases, according to Capanaga (2002:71). Recently, *de-* has been revitalised due to the English influence and appears in *detoxificar*: "Revitaliza, *detoxifica* e ilumina. (*Germaine de Capuccini*, June 2017); *detoxificante* "Su poder antiarrugas y *detoxificante*, reafirma la piel de los párpados (*Natura Bissé*, June 2017)"; *detoxificador* "Antioxidante, detoxificador y reestructurador cutáneo. (*Farma Dorsch*, June 2017)"; but also in *detoxificación*: 1) "supone un notable avance en la *detoxificación* celular" (*Germaine de Capuccini*, June 2017)"; 2) "una *desintoxicación* sobre un árbol, que incluye yoga, sesiones de entrenamiento privadas, zumos depurativos y mucho más. (*Aire Libre*, March 2018).

Table 3. Prefixes *de-*, *des-*, and *dis-* in dictionaries and corpora

Spanish item	DLE 1992	DLE 2001	DLE online	CORDE	CREA	English item	OED	BNC
desintoxicación	✓	✓	✓	✓1948	✓1989	detoxication	✓1905	✓1985
detoxificación	X	X	X	X	✓1986	detoxification	X	✓1985
detoxificador	X	X	X	X	X	detoxicator	✓1906	X
detoxificante	X	X	X	X	X	detoxifying/ detoxifier	X	✓1985
detoxificar	X	X	X	X	✓1996	detoxify	✓1905	✓1985
distrés	X	X	X	X	✓1986	distress	✓1297	✓1985

Only *desintoxicación* is recorded in the three versions of the DLE, and in the CREA and CORDE corpora. The rest of the items appear in the English sources, the OED and the BNC. The cases of *detoxificación* and *detoxificar*, both recorded in the CREA, are not appropriate in Spanish according to FundéuRAE: "what in English

⁶ Authors' translation of "no se consideran ortográficamente adecuadas las grafías en las que el prefijo aparece unido con guion a la palabra base (**anti-mafia, *anti-cancerígeno*) o separado por ella por un espacio en blanco (*anti mafia, anti cancerígeno*)" (2010:535).

is called *detoxification*, in Spanish is called *desintoxicación* or *deshabitación*”.⁷ The attestation of *detoxify* and *detoxification* as early as 1905 in the OED points to the influence of the English language in this group of derived words in Spanish.

Currently, due to the COVID19 restrictions, a frequent term in the Spanish media is *desescalada*, which is not documented in the latest version of the DLE. The English counterpart *de-escalation* has been recorded in the OED since 1965 and the verb *de-escalate* since 1964. The FundéuRAE states that both nouns and the verb *escalar*, as well as its antonym *desescalar* — which are used for conflicts, violence, tension or confrontation with the meaning of ‘enlarge, raise/rise, make something grow’ and ‘decrease, reduce, make something diminish’, respectively — have acquired those meanings from the influence of the English *to escalate* (which the *Oxford Dictionary* defines as ‘augment, rise, increase rapidly’).⁸

Hiper- Apart from the core meaning of ‘large’, there are other additional meanings in Spanish for this prefix. According to the *Nueva gramática de la lengua española* (*New Grammar of the Spanish Language*, RAE 2009:186), “the prefix *hiper-* denotes excess, either in the intensity with which something happens (*hiperactividad*) or in the quantity or the degree to which a quality is attributed (*hipervitaminosis*)”.⁹ Spanish owes words like *hipermedia*, *hipertexto*, *hipervínculo*, *hipersensible* to the English language (Pratt 1980:188). However, today *hiper-* is also used as an intensifier similar to *super-* to mean ‘over, above, beyond’. In fact, *hiper-* overlaps with the hyperbolic *super-*. Thus, depending on the Spanish speakers’ preferences, they may use *superbonito* or *hiperbonito*. *Mega-* is also acquiring this new meaning, whereby *hiperrápido*, *megarápido*, *superrápido* and *ultrarápido* are possible. There seems to be a gradation in the intensity in *super-*, *mega-*, *hiper-* and *ultra-*, although not all of them fit with all adjectives and their use is a matter of the linguistic preference of the speakers. Subsequently, some speakers may choose a given prefix to convey the idea of ‘beyond’—*super-*, *mega-*, *hiper-* and *ultra-*, while others may prefer to use a different one. The influence of the English language on the development of this meaning for *mega-* is hard to prove. Regarding the lexical units containing *hiper-*, the examples extracted from the corpus can be consulted in Table 4.

⁷ Authors’ translation of “lo que en inglés se llama *detoxification*, en español se denomina *desintoxicación* o *deshabitación*” at <https://www.fundeu.es/consulta/detoxification-1352/>

⁸ Authors’ translation of “Tanto estos sustantivos como el verbo *escalar* y su antónimo *desescalar* —que se usan referidos sobre todo a conflictos, violencia, tensión o confrontación con los sentidos de ‘ampliar, elevar, hacer crecer algo’ y ‘rebajar, reducir, hacer disminuir algo’, respectivamente— han adquirido estos significados por influencia del inglés *to escalate* (que el diccionario de Oxford define como ‘aumentar, subir, incrementarse algo rápidamente’)” at <https://www.fundeu.es/recomendacion/escalar-escalada-aumento-incremento/>

⁹ Authors’ translation of “El prefijo *hiper-* denota exceso, sea en la intensidad con que sucede algo (*hiperactividad*) o en la cantidad o el grado que se atribuye a una propiedad (*hipervitaminosis*)”.

Table 4. Prefix *hiper-* in dictionaries and corpora

Spanish item	DLE 1992	DLE 2001	DLE online	CORDE	CREA	English item	OED	BNC
hiperactividad	X	✓	✓	✓1912	✓1980	hyperactivity	✓1888	✓1975
hipersensible	✓	✓	✓	✓1919	✓1976	hypersensitive	✓1914	✓1985
hipertensión	✓	✓	✓	✓1912	✓1975	hypertension	✓1939	✓1985
hipertexto	X	✓	✓	X	✓1995	hypertext	✓1965	✓1985
hipervínculo	X	X	✓	X	✓2000	hyperlink	✓1988	X

As evidenced by the data in Table 4, only two items from our corpus are recorded in the 1992 version of the DLE (*hipersensible*, *hipertensión*), four in the second print version (*hiperactividad*, *hipersensible*, *hipertensión*, *hipertexto*) and all five in the online dictionary. The five items are also found in the CREA, whereas only three are recorded in the CORDE (*hiperactividad*, *hipersensible*, *hipertensión*). If we compare the first time their English counterparts are documented, it is prior to the record of the words in Spanish, with the exception of the medical term *hipertensión*, which is recorded earlier in Spanish.

Inter- is considered the learned allomorph of *entre-*. Although it is a common prefix in the history of Spanish, according to Capanaga (2002:73), this prefix is at its peak now, especially with the meaning of ‘relationship’. Thus, ANGLICOR records *interactivo*, *interface*, *interfaz* and the ubiquitous form *internet*, which could have been *entrededes* if it had been coined in Spanish originally. Thus, thanks to *internet*, Spanish uses *interconectar*, *interconexión*, *interconectividad*:

(8) «A medida que la globalización, la *interconectividad* y el crecimiento de las clases medias hagan que cada vez más personas viajen, el mundo seguirá pareciendo más pequeño y la inclusión se convertirá en una prioridad aún mayor», afirmó el Secretario General de la OMT, Zurab Pololikashvili. (*Aire Libre*, November 2018).

The locative prefix *inter-* is currently productive and “is supported by strong adoption in the technical register” (Lang 1990:175), as can be seen in the examples provided in Table 5.

Table 5. Prefix *inter-* in dictionaries and corpora

Spanish item	DLE 1992	DLE 2001	DLE online	CORDE	CREA	English item	OED	BNC
interactivo	✓	✓	✓	X	✓1992	interactive	✓1972	✓
interconectar	X	✓	✓	X	✓1978	interconnect	✓1865	✓
interconectividad	X	X	X	X	X	interconnectivity	X	✓1985
interconexión	X	✓	✓	✓1957	✓1989	interconnection	✓1856	✓
interfaz	✓	✓	✓	X	✓1992	interface	✓1965	✓
internet	X	X	✓	X	✓1995	internet	✓1974	✓1985

As shown in the table, five out of the six items appear in the online version of the DLE (*interactivo*, *interconectar*, *interconexión*, *interfaz*, *internet*), whereas only two were included in the 1992 version: *interactivo* and *interfaz*. In turn, their six

English counterparts are registered in the BNC and five in the OED. In all cases, the English entries antedate the first occurrence of the Spanish words in the consulted sources. Again, it could be pointed out that the use of the prefix in these derived words in European Spanish is due to the influence of the creations in the English language.

Mini- and **maxi-**. The former prefix has two main values: the sense of ‘short’ present in *minifalda*, a calque from *mini-skirt*, a type of garment launched by the British designer Mary Quant in 1965 (Lorenzo 1996:296); and a second meaning of ‘very short’ either in space, time or quantity, as in *minibar*, *minibús*, *minibreak*, *minicolección*, *miniclub*, *minifútbol*, *mini gymkhana*, *miniraid* and *miniserie*. The opposite prefix in meaning is *maxi-*, but this form is not recorded as frequently, unless we search for creations in fashion where forms like *maxianillo*, *maxi-brazalete*, *maxi falda*, *maxigargantilla*, *maxijersey* and *maxiplataformas* are documented (Estornell-Pons 2012:81). Our own examples for both prefixes in the field of fashion include:

- (9) Los ‘it bags’ todavía interesan, pero en el último año el protagonismo es para sus *minitallas* (*VOGUE*, February 2017).
- (10) Sus *minivestidos* triunfan entre las ‘celebs’ más atrevidas (*VOGUE*, February 2017).
- (11) *Minifalda* vaquera con efecto ‘patchwork’ (*ELLE*, February 2017).
- (12) ...ella llamaba la atención por sus hombreras y sus *maxijoyas* al lado de aquel genio pop de pelo blanco (*ELLE*, February 2017).

Table 6. Prefixes *maxi-* and *mini-* in dictionaries and corpora

Spanish item	DLE 1992	DLE 2001	DLE online	CORDE	CREA	English item	OED	BNC
maxi falda	X	X	X	✓1972 unseparated	✓1983 unseparated	maxi-skirt	✓1966	X
maxianillo	X	X	X	X	X	maxi-ring	X	X
maxi-brazalete	X	X	X	X	X	maxi-bracelet	X	X
maxigargantilla	X	X	X	X	X	maxi-necklace	X	X
maxijersey	X	X	X	X	X	maxi-jumper maxi-sweater	X	X
maxijoyas	X	X	X	X	X	maxi-jewel	X	X
maxiplataformas	X	X	X	X	X	maxi-platform	X	X
minicolección	X	X	X	X	✓2003	minicollection	X	X
minivacaciones	X	X	X	X	✓1985	mini-break	✓1968	✓1985
minifalda	✓	✓	✓	✓1966	✓1988	miniskirt mini-skirt	✓1962	✓1975
minicámara	X	X	X	X	✓1995	minicam	✓1977	X
minilibro	X	X	X	X	X	minibook	X	X
miniserie	X	X	X	X	✓1989	miniseries	✓1963	✓1985
minitallas	X	X	X	X	✓1987	minisizes	X	X
minivestidos	X	X	X	✓1972	✓1991	minidress	✓1965	✓1985

Examining the examples that contain both prefixes more closely, there are clear differences. Only one derivative word coined with the prefix *maxi-* (*maxi falda*) appears in the two Spanish corpora. The English *maxi-skirt* is registered in the OED in 1966, prior to the first record in Spanish. The rest of the items do not appear in any of the English sources consulted for this study. Therefore, the new coined derivatives in Spanish with this prefix cannot be considered related to the creation of similar words in English.

The analysis of the cases with *mini-* shows different results. Although only one out of eight is included in the three versions of the DLE (*minifalda*), seven items (*minicolección*, *minivacaciones*, *minifalda*, *minicámara*, *miniseries*, *minitallas*, *minivestidos*) have been found in CREA, indicating that these words are used in the Spanish language. In fact, *minifalda* and *minivestido* are also recorded in the CORDE since 1966 and 1972 respectively. Their English equivalents are found in the OED and the BNC prior to their appearance in Spanish. In addition, the words *mini-break*, *minicam* and *miniseries* are recorded in the OED before their first use in the Spanish sources checked. The word *minitallas* appears only in the CREA and in none of the other sources used. Therefore, the English influence in the process of formation cannot be attested in the case of *minitallas*, though the data can prove a possible influence of the use of the prefix for other words coined in European Spanish.

Multi- is a Latin prefix that has little impact on the traditional dictionaries, according to Capanaga (2002:77), who records *multicolor*, *multiforme*, *multicopiar*, *multinacional*, *multimillonario*. However, today it is a powerful device in the creation of neologisms, since it appears frequently combined with both noun and adjective bases, such as in *multiactividad*, *multiaventura*, *multidisciplinar* and *multifacético*:

- (13) Pack *multiactividad* en la nieve: ruta en moto de nieve o mushing, construcción de un iglú, cena en refugio de montaña, dormir en iglú, desayuno (*Aire Libre*, January/February 2018).
- (14) Ofertas combinadas de alojamiento rural y distintas actividades de *multiaventura*: senderismo, rutas de bicicleta, descenso de barrancos, raid, escalada... (Revista Ibérica).
- (15) Esta bien llamada filosofía octogonal ha encontrado su sede en esta clínica comandada por el prestigioso traumatólogo y cirujano ortopédico Ignacio Varo, quien la define como un centro *multidisciplinar* 360° que se diferencia del resto porque aúna diferentes especialidades que tradicionalmente se han trabajado individualmente (*Top Viajes*, June 2019).
- (16) Silversea ha presentado su nueva Photo Academy en sus viajes a la Antártida a bordo de Silver Cloud utilizando el nuevo estudio fotográfico del barco como centro para el programa de enriquecimiento *multifacético* (*Aire Libre*, January/February 2018).

Even though lexical units containing the prefix *multi-* may seem to have been in use for a long time, Lorenzo (1996:596) had previously discussed the foreign nature of some of them. This is not so evident in *multimillonario* (first recorded in American English in 1855-60 in the OED), *multicolor* (also in American English in 1840-50) or *multilateral* (1690-1700).

Table 7. Prefix *multi-* in dictionaries and corpora

Spanish item	DLE 1992	DLE 2001	DLE online	CORDE	CREA	English item	OED	BNC
multiactividad	X	X	X	X	X	multi-activity	✓1943	✓1985
multiaventura	X	X	X	X	✓2003	multi-adventure	X	X
multicolor	✓	✓	✓	✓1906	✓1987	multicolour	✓1842	✓1985
multicultural	X	✓	✓	X	✓1994	multicultural	✓1935	✓1985
multiculturalidad	X	X	✓	X	✓1994	multiculturalism	✓1957	X
multidisciplinar	X	✓	X	X	✓1996	multidisciplinary	✓1944	✓1985
multifacético	X	X	X	✓1965	✓1977	multifaceted	✓1870	✓1985
multifuncional	X	X	✓	X	✓1975	multifunctional	✓1934	✓1985
multilateral	✓	✓	✓	✓1896	✓1982	multilateral	✓1606	✓1985
multinacional	✓	✓	✓	✓1974	✓1980	multinational	✓1854	✓1985
multisectorial	X	X	X	X	✓1985	multisectoral	✓1953	✓1985

As for the analysis of the data in Table 7, an increasing number of words with the prefix *multi-* is included in the online version". In fact, seven out of twelve items, compared to the three items recorded in the first version of this dictionary (*multicolor*, *multilateral*, *multinacional*). All but one of the examples (*multiactividad*) have been found in the CREA. Most of the English items in the table, except *multi-adventure* and *multimedia*, are recorded in the OED always prior to the first use in the Spanish sources. This example, *multiaventura*, only appears in the CREA used at the beginning of 21st century, the newest creation in European Spanish. Regarding the rest of the examples that were extracted, all were created first in English, and therefore one could point to the possibility of the influence of the English language in the formation of these words in European Spanish.

Super- According to Lázaro-Carreter (1999), until the 18th century there were very few words taken from Latin containing this prefix: *superabundante*, *superbisimo*, *superficial*, *superfluo*, *superior*. In 1803, the *Diccionario de la lengua española* introduced *supereminente* and in 1884, there is an entry tagging *super* as preposition, as in *superabundante* and a modern word: *superfino* (Lázaro-Carreter 1999). In 1970 its status was changed from preposition to Spanish constituent ("formante castellano"). In 1992, *superelegante* was added to the *Dictionary*. In the 1940s, other combinations entered the language due to American influence: *superpetrolero*, *supercompetencia*, *supercombustible*, *superbombardero*, *supersónico*, *superconductor*, *supersíntesis*. This way, *super-* became an essential device in marketing and publicity, since every product was endowed with superpowers by adding this initial element. Thus, this prefix is found in calques, such as *superestrella* from *superstar*, but is also attached to adjectives as in

superguay, *supertriste* and adverbs, as in *superbién* and *supermal*. Examples from ANGLICOR include the following:

- (17) La primera vez que vi de cerca los *superpoderes* del deporte fue en febrero de 2013 (*Cosmopolitan*, April 2020).
- (18) ...una novela *superdivertida* (*Cosmopolitan*, April 2020).
- (19) ...forman parte ya de la colección de pasarelas más increíbles de la *supermodelo* (*Top Viajes*, April 2018).
- (20) El *superpopular* Medusa se realiza con una sola perforación justo en la zona cóncava que forma el arco de cupido (*Glamour*, May/June 2020).

All in all, Lorenzo (1996) adds that it is difficult to determine the real importance of the English language in the creation and diffusion of neologisms with the prefix *super-*. The etymological origin of new formations with *super-* as an augmentative seems to be unclear not only in Spanish but also in other languages, such as German (Onysko 2007:225).¹⁰ Thus, according to Lorenzo (1996:435-436), *supervisar*, *supermán*, *superproducción*, *superventa*, *superagente*, *superfortaleza volante*, *superpotencias*, *supertanque*, *superlight*, *superjumbo* and *superwoman* clearly come from the English language. He also mentions that it is difficult to be sure that some technicisms can be ascribed to English and wonders about the original language upon which *supernova*, *superterodino*, *supersincrotón* and *superteleobjetivo* were based.

Table 8. Prefix *super-* in dictionaries and corpora

Spanish item	DLE 1992	DLE 2001	DLE online	CORDE	CREA	English item	OED	BNC
superalimento	X	X	X	X	X	superfood	✓1915	X
superaprendizaje	X	X	X	X	X	superlearning	X	X
superbrillante	X	X	X	X	X	super-smart	✓1870	X
superelegante	X	X	X	X	✓1975	super-smart	✓ ?1750	X
superespecial	X	X	X	X	✓1994	super-special	X	X
superfeliz	X	X	X	X	✓2001	superhappy	✓	X
superfino	✓	X	X	✓1763	✓1999	superthin	X	X
superguay	X	X	X	X	✓1990	super-cool	✓1915	✓
superhéroe	X	X	✓	X	✓1990	superhero	✓1899	✓
superintensivo	X	X	X	X	X	superintensive	X	✓
supermodelo	X	X	✓	X	✓1977	supermodel	✓1967	✓ 1985
superperfeccionista	X	X	X	X	X	superperfeccionista	X	X
superpoderes	X	X	✓	X	✓1979	superpopular	✓1894	✓
superpopular	X	X	X	X	✓2004	supermodel	X	X

¹⁰ “While *Mega-* and *Super-* seem most productive, their equivalent functions as augmentatives in English blur the distinction between prefixation in German and borrowing of lexical units already derived in English (e.g. *megacity*, *megastar*, *supercomputer*, *superpower*, *superstar*, and *superwoman*) (Onysko 2007:225).

superproducción	✓	✓	✓	✓1923	✓1989	superproduction	X	X
superrentable	X	X	X	X	X	superprofitable superworthwhile	X X	X X
supertodo terreno	X	X	X	X	X	super-SUV super 4x4	X	X X
superyate	X	X	X	X	X	superyacht	X	X

The prefix *super-* can be classified as a locative and intensifier. As Lang (1990:176) notes this prefix “frequently deviates from the purely ‘locative’ sense to convey excess of the base and so take on a superlative or hyperbolic dimension” and, besides, “is one of the most prolific prefixes of this group, much abused in the hyperbolic language of journalism” (Lang 1990:180). This hyperbolic use has also permeated the general language as the examples from the corpus show. In fact, *super-* is the element which occurs most frequently in our list of items as it appears nineteen times and, in all cases, it is superlative or hyperbolic in nature. Regarding their inclusion in the DLE, the number of items has doubled from the 1992 version, from two elements (*superfino* and *superproducción*) to four elements (*superhéroe*, *supermodelo*, *superpoderes*, *superproducción*) in the current online version, though one of the items, *superfino*, has disappeared in the latest version of the dictionary. When checking the CREA and CORDE corpora, up to ten items have been found in the first one but only two in the latter (*superfino*, *superproducción*). Five of the examples extracted from our corpus are not included in any of the Spanish sources nor their English counterparts (*superaprendizaje*, *superperfeccionista*, *superrentable*, *supertodoterreno*, *superyate*). Besides, regarding the five items recorded in the CREA (*superespecial*, *superfino*, *superpopular*, *superproducción*), their English equivalents do not appear in the two English sources used for this study. Even though the five items recorded in both languages were coined first in English (*superelegant*, *supercool*, *superhero*, *supermodel*, *superpowers*), nine items seem to have been created in Spanish (*superaprendizaje*, *superespecial*, *superfino*, *superperfeccionista*, *superpopular*, *superproducción*, *superrentable*, *supertodoterreno*, *superyate*), so the influence of the English language in this process of word creation using the prefix *super-* cannot be clearly determined.

Ultra- According to the *Nueva gramática de la lengua española* (RAE 2009:181), *ultra-* has two meanings: one related to the space that goes beyond a certain limit (*ultramar*, *ultratumba*) and, in a metaphorical sense, what goes beyond the qualities designated by the base noun (*ultrasonido*). It is also a highly productive prefix in the latter meaning:

- (21) Contemplar diseño y decoración en este recinto corrobora la idea de que se trata de un complejo rural de *ultralujo* que nada tiene que ver con un hotel tradicional de alta gama (*Top Viajes*, June 2018).
 (22) ...plataneras y el camino de ruta volcánica, parte del *ultramaratón* la Transvulcania (*Top Viajes*, July/August 2018).

(23) Peugeot, y su división de *ultradiseño* Peugeot Design Lab, han creado la colección de equipajes y artículos de cuero definitiva para los viajeros más habituales que no descuidan la elegancia y la prestancia (*Top viajes*, October, 2018).

Similarly, it is attached to adjective bases with the meaning of ‘beyond’, but can also intensify the quality of the adjective and it is equivalent to ‘extremely’ in this sense. This usage is especially noticeable in some of the examples below (*ultra corrector*, *ultradelgado*, *ultra-dosificado*, *ultraligero*, *ultrarreparador*, *ultrarresistente*, *ultrarrealista*, *ultravioleta*):

(24) Tras exfoliar con Suave exfoliante labios y contorno aplicar *Ultra-corrector* voluminizador labios y contorno mediante suaves (*Germaine de Capuccini*, June 2017).

(25) ...este tratamiento *ultra-dosificado* anti-manchas actúa sobre las manchas oscuras de rostro, cuello, escote y manos (*Germaine de Capuccini*, June 2017).

(26) Un bolso de diseño italiano súper actual y *ultradelgado*, con todas las características de la colección (*Top Viajes*, April 2018).

(27) El espíritu vintage se suma al diseño geométrico y *ultraligero* en el modelo que protagoniza la nueva campaña de gafas de sol Chloé, una propuesta con cristales octogonales que subrayan la característica principal del nuevo concepto «Poppy» (*Top Viajes*, January 2018).

(28) Bálsamo natural *ultrarreparador*. Exclusivo bálsamo fundente cuya fórmula 100% natural combina la riqueza nutritiva de las mantecas naturales de Mango y Karité con los aceites esenciales de Mandarina y la hoja de Olivo (*Natura Bissé*, June 2017).

(29) Fabricado en nylon *ultrarresistente*, dispone del característico bolsillo extraíble que es la marca de la colección WO3 (*Top Viajes*, March 2018).

(30) Durante el invierno la piel no solo sufre las consecuencias del frío y los cambios bruscos de temperatura, sino también de la contaminación, la radiación *ultravioleta*, las calefacciones, los excesos en la alimentación y el siempre presente estrés, por lo que mantenerse fiel a un ritual de cuidados adecuado, que cuide y proteja nuestra piel en profundidad, es fundamental (*Top Viajes*, February 2018).

In the case of *ultrarrealista* or *ultra realista*, the novelty of the neologism is attested for the fact that the same publication writes it either as one single word or two different words: “La VR, o realidad virtual, transporta a los visitantes, con Sébastien Loeb Racing Xpérience al volante, a vivir una aventura *ultrarrealista*.” (*Top Viajes*, March 2018); “En esta aventura *ultra realista*, nada se pasa por alto, ni el humo en los derrapajes controlados, ni el estrés de perder el antídoto, ni las aceleraciones amplificadas por los efectos de sonido y de viento (*Top Viajes*, July/August 2018).

Table 9. Prefix *ultra-* in dictionaries and corpora

Spanish item	DLE 1992	DLE 2001	DLE online	CORDE	CREA	English item	OED	BNC
ultracorrector	X	X	X	X	X	ultracorrector	X	X
ultradelgado	X	X	X	X	X	ultrathin	✓1949	✓
ultradiseño	X	X	X	X	X	ultradesign	X	X
ultra-dosificado	X	X	X	X	X	ultra-dosified	X	X
ultraligero	✓	✓	✓	X	✓1985	ultralight	✓1974	✓
ultralujo	X	X	X	X	✓2004	ultraluxury	X	X
ultramaratón	X	X	X	X	X	ultra-marathon	✓1977	X
ultrarreparador	X	X	X	X	X	ultrarepairing	X	X
ultrarealista	X	X	X	X	X	ultrarealist	X	X
ultrarresistente	X	X	X	X	X	ultraresistant	X	X
ultrasonido	✓	✓	✓	✓1957	✓1983	ultrasound	✓1923	✓
ultravioleta	✓	✓	✓	✓1929	✓1975	ultraviolet	✓1840	✓

The prefix *ultra-* also overlaps with the function of the prefix *super-* and “is active in specialised technical fields such as physics and electronics” (Lang 1990:181). We have indeed found that most words from the corpus are related to specialised fields, but their inclusion in the DLE has not changed in the last three decades, since only three of these lexical units (*ultraligero*, *ultrasonido* and *ultravioleta*) appear in the three versions. These three examples have been crosschecked in CREA, which also documents the item *ultralujo*, and in the CORDE, which records only two items, *ultrasonido* and *ultravioleta*. Although the prefix is productive in the creation of new Spanish words, these lexical units are not recorded in the DLE.

As for the English counterparts, five items with the prefix *ultra-* appear in the OED: *ultrathin* (*ultradelgado*), *ultralight* (*ultraligero*), *ultra-marathon* (*ultramaratón*), *ultrasound* (*ultrasonido*), and *ultraviolet* (*ultravioleta*). In all the five cases they were recorded prior to the appearance of Spanish words in the consulted sources. Therefore, it could be claimed that the creation of these derivative words reflects the structure of the English words. In fact, the word *ultradelgado* was included in the *Diccionario de Neologismos del Español Actual* in 2013 (Sánchez et al. 2016), when some other neologisms coined with the prefix *ultra-* were also incorporated. In addition, we have found an example, *ultra-dosificado*, which follows the orthographic rules of the English language that do not coincide with those of the Spanish language regarding the use of prefixes.

3.2 Prefixoids

The elements included in this section are learned constituents that usually take the initial position, although not exclusively. They tend to be grouped separately from prefixes under the common denomination of *prefixoids* (Lang 1990:181) and are elements that can occur as independent lexemes but also bound to stems. The controversy regarding the group of prefixoids – also called *affixoids* (Dimela and Ralli 2012:148) – can be attested to in a number of studies.¹¹ Affixoids are situated

¹¹ See, for instance, Yañez-López (2014:79-85).

in between affixes and stems, and in between the processes of compounding and affixation. Varela Ortega and Martín García (1999:4997) distinguish this group of elements from prefixes and they include some classic elements (*hemo-globina, fotosíntesis, eco-nomía*) within this group, but also modern clippings (*euro-diputado, tardo-franquismo*). Moreover, Lang (1990:184) underscores "the increasing popularity of these constituents, which tends to extend beyond their initially specialised lexical fields, and, notwithstanding the foreign origin of many of the formations in which they appear".

Indeed, it is a moot issue which elements should be included as affixation devices, since not all scholars agree. Thus, **eco-** is sometimes viewed as a clipping from *ecologic* (Estornell-Pons 2012:91) and **video-** is not without controversy either. Our aim here is not to determine the true nature of those elements, but to show how their use in Spanish can be influenced by English. Capanaga (2002) also includes here learned elements like *bio-*, which are highly productive in medicine and health-related disciplines, and *euro-*, an item that has proliferated since Spain became a member of the European Union (formerly European Community).

Agro- is a learned stem that can appear in nouns like *agroturismo*: "ECOTUR integrado en redes internacionales de *agroturismo* y ecoturismo, propone 100 iniciativas de turismo rural y agroturismo ecológico, comprometidas con el desarrollo rural sostenible" (*Aire Libre*, January/February 2018), and also in adjectives, such as *agroecológico*: "Estos bosques cuentan con servicios ecosistémicos que proporcionan a ciudades como Quito, Los Bancos y Pedro Vicente Maldonado fuentes de agua potable, producción *agroecológica* y generación de energía eléctrica" (*Top Viajes*, September 2018).

Table 10. Prefixoid *agro-* in dictionaries and corpora

Spanish item	DLE 1992	DLE 2001	DLE online	CORDE	CREA	English item	OED	BNC
agroecológico	X	X	✓	X	✓2002	agroecological	✓1940	X
agroturismo	X	X	✓	X	✓1994	agrotourism	✓1987	X

The two examples with *agro-* have been incorporated into the current online version of the DLE, whereas none was present in the previous paper versions. Both also appear in the CREA, but none in the CORDE. As they are recorded in the OED prior to the first appearance in the CREA, we could also point out the influence of the English language in their formation.

Ciber- The OED records *cybernetics* in 1948 in a quotation by Wiener: "We have decided to call the entire field of control and communication theory, whether in the machine or in the animal, by the name Cybernetics" (*Cybernetics*, 1948:19). This discipline was adapted into Spanish as *cibernética*. From this moment onwards, we have documented *cibercafé* in numerous publications, but also *cibercrimen, cibercultura, ciberespacio, cibernauta, ciberregalo*:

(31) Puede seleccionar su asiento e imprimir su tarjeta de embarque on line directamente desde el ordenador de su propio domicilio, oficina o *cibercafé* (Ronda, March 2008).

(32) Incluso se podrá pensar que los *cibercafés* están concebidos más para estudiantes (Personal Computer Plus, January 2004).

(33) Ejecutivos del *cibercrimen* (QUO, March 2008).

(34) Pero sin duda, el reclamo más atractivo son los llamados *ciberregalos* (Personal Computer Plus, January 2004).

Table 11. Prefixoid ciber- in dictionaries and corpora

Spanish item	DLE 1992	DLE 2001	DLE online	CORDE	CREA	English item	OED	BNC
cibercafé	X	X	✓	X	✓1997	cybercafe	✓ 1994	X
cibercrimen	X	X	X	X	X	cybercrime	✓ 1991	X
cibercultura	X	X	✓	X	✓1997	cyberculture	✓ 1963	X
ciberespacio	X	✓	✓	X	✓1995	cyberspace	✓ 1982	✓1985
cibernauta	X	✓	✓	X	✓1995	cybernaut	✓ 1965	X
cibernética	X	✓	✓	✓1952	✓1975	cybernetics	✓ 1948	✓1975
ciberregalo	X	X	X	X	X	cyberpresent cybergift	X	X

In the case of *ciber-*, none of the examples appears in the first paper version of the DLE, three in the second (*ciberespacio*, *cibernauta*, *cibernética*) and five out of seven cases are in the current online version and also in the CREA; that represents a clear progression, and all the examples are related to an English borrowed word in Spanish, *cibernética*. Almost all the English items are recorded in the OED; only *ciberregalo* (*cyberpresent/cybergift*) is not present in this source. The relationship between the English word-formation process and the Spanish word-formation process seems to be clear.

Eco- is one of those items that can be considered a prefix producing derivatives or an educated stem giving rise to compounds (Varela 2005:73). As FundeuRae explains: "In the specific case of *eco-*, the academic dictionary incorporates the meaning of 'ecology' in its twenty-third edition, absent in previous editions, which only included the senses of 'house, dwelling, living environment' and 'electromagnetic wave, reflected sound'".¹²

When *eco-* is combined with other elements, the result is usually a noun, as in *ecoturismo*, or even together with *agro-* in *ecoagroturismo*, or the Anglicism *ecolodge*. It also appears with adjective bases, as in *ecológico* and *eco-sostenible*, which are not recorded in the OED, as the following example illustrates "Se trata de la mejor alternativa *eco-sostenible* para sustituir las partículas de polietileno usadas comúnmente por la industria cosmética" (*Farma Dorsch*, June 2017).

¹² Authors' translation of "En el caso concreto de *eco-*, el diccionario académico incorpora el significado de 'ecología' en su vigesimotercera edición, ausente en ediciones anteriores, que solo recogían los sentidos de 'casa, morada, ámbito vital' y 'onda electromagnética, sonido reflejado'" at <https://www.fundeu.es/recomendacion/eco-ecotasa-ecoparque-ecotaxi-ecoterrorista-ecopacifista/>

Table 12. Prefixoid *eco-* in dictionaries and corpora

Spanish item	DLE 1992	DLE 2001	DLE online	CORDE	CREA	English item	OED	BNC
ecoagroturismo	X	X	X	X	X	eco-agrotourism	X	X
ecosistema	✓	✓	✓	✓1968	✓1989	ecosystem	✓1935	✓1985
eco-sostenible	X	X	X	X	X	ecosustainable	X	X
ecoturismo	X	✓	✓	X	✓1994	ecotourism	✓1982	✓1985

As shown in Table 12, two examples with the prefixoid *eco-* appear in the online version of the DLE (*ecosistema*, *ecoturismo*); one of the examples, *ecosistema*, is included in all three versions of the dictionary and the example *ecoturismo* can be found in the latest paper version and the online one. Both are also present in the CREA and the first one, *ecosistema*, in the CORDE. Regarding the English items, (*eco-agrotourism* and *ecotourism*) are recorded in the OED and the BNC prior to their use in European Spanish. In the case of *eco-sostenible*, the indication of FundéuRAE regarding the orthography is that “the compositional element *eco-*, which means ‘ecology’ among other things, (...) is written together with the word to which it is incorporated, **without a hyphen or space in between**”,¹³ being a sign of the English influence in its formation when the hyphen is used. Once again, the relationship between the English word-formation process and the Spanish word-formation process seems to be a plausible possibility.

Nano- and **micro-**. *Nano-* is a classic element that designates “a unit of measurement to denote a factor of 10^{-9} (one thousand-millionth)”, according to the OED. It can be combined with nouns, as in *nanotecnología*, *nanoestructura* and *nanotubo*. *Micro-*, which according to the OED means “small (often microscopic) or relatively small size”, is used in *microchip*, *micrófono*, and *microondas*. Some cases found in our corpus are *microrrelieve*, *microcirculación*, and *microinyecciones*, as the examples illustrate:¹⁴

(35) Consiguiendo que el *microrrelieve* cutáneo se alise, la dermis recupere firmeza y se atenúen las discromías de la piel (*Germaine Capuccini*, June 2017).

(36) Refuerza su capacidad de generación de energía, y cafeína, con gran poder drenante, lipolítico y estimulador de la *microcirculación* (*Germaine Capuccini*, June 2017).

¹³ Authors’ translation of “El elemento compositivo *eco-*, que significa entre otras cosas ‘ecología’, (...) se escribe unido a la palabra a la que se incorpora, **sin guion ni espacio intermedios**” at <https://www.fundeu.es/recomendacion/eco-ecotasa-ecoparque-ecotaxi-ecoterrorista-ecopacifista/>

¹⁴ Even if France is a landmark in the fashion world, the exposure of European Spanish speakers to the French language is nothing compared to English. English has been promoted as the first foreign language in Spain since 1970 and students since their early years are immersed in the so-called bilingual programmes in English and Spanish since 2003. Social media interactions, the film industry, academic exchanges and business transactions, among many other activities, are performed in English on a daily basis in Spain.

(37) Sin recurrir a *micro-inyecciones*, Timexpert Rides es la alternativa eficaz frente a la cirugía (Germaine Capuccini, June 2017).

In the last example, as can be seen in the examples of prefixes and prefixoids which were explained previously, the influence of the English language “also appears in the orthographical patterns of Spanish derivatives and neoclassical compounds” (Tejedor-Martínez 2017:316). As the Royal Academy of the Spanish Language indicates that “it is not considered orthographically correct when the prefix is joined to its base by a hyphen (**anti-mafia*, **anti-cancerígeno*) or separated from it by a blank space (*anti mafia*, *anti cancerígeno*)” (RAE 2010: 535).¹⁵

Table 13. Prefixoids *micro-* and *nano-* in dictionaries and corpora

Spanish item	DLE 1992	DLE 2001	DLE online	CORDE	CREA	English item	OED	BNC
microcirculación	X	X	X	X	✓1988	micro-circulation	✓1955	✓1985
micro-inyecciones	X	X	X	X	X	micro-jabs micro-injections	✓1921	X
microrelieve	X	X	X	X	X	micro-relief	✓1926	X
nanoestructura	X	X	✓	X	X	nanostructure	✓1978	X
nanotecnología	X	X	✓	X	✓1991	nanotechnology	✓1974	✓1985
nanotubo	X	X	✓	X	✓2003	nanotube	✓1992	✓1985

In the case of *micro-*, none of the three examples with the prefixoid *micro-* appears in any of the versions of the DLE and only one, *microcirculación*, is present in the CREA. Unlike the Spanish dictionary which we consulted, the OED includes the three English equivalents and *micro-circulation* was recorded in 1955, before it was registered in the Spanish DLE. Regarding the examples with the prefixoid *nano-*, the three items appear in the online version of the DLE (*nanoestructura*, *nanotecnología*, *nanotube*), two in the CREA (*nanotecnología*, *nanotube*) and none in the CORDE. All the English counterparts are recorded in the OED before their occurrence in European Spanish sources. Thus, the influence of the English language in the use of these prefixoids in the word creation in European Spanish can be presumed.

video- Although scholars such as Lorenzo (1996:465) consider *video* to be a compound element (“elemento compositivo”), Lang (1990:184) argues that it is a prefixoid, and points out that “the multiplicity of *video-* terms is the direct outcome of a new technology”, and that it is attached to foreign words or native stems, as in the examples from our corpus (*videocámara*, *video-consola*, *videoconferencia*, *videojuego*).

¹⁵ Authors’ translation of “no se consideran ortográficamente adecuadas las graffias en las que el prefijo aparece unido con guion a la palabra base (**anti-mafia*, **anti-cancerígeno*) o separado por ella por un espacio en blanco (*anti mafia*, *anti cancerígeno*)” (2010: 535).

(38) Completa sus instalaciones con 2 restaurantes con servicio buffet libre (sólo servicio desayuno y cenas), bar temático “L’Automòbil” y bar automático, zona Fitness y Wellness (piscina adultos, piscina infantil, jacuzzi, sauna, baño turco y sala Fitness con máquinas de musculación y Fitness), parque infantil y sala de *video-consolas* (gratuito), salas de reuniones, aparcamiento privado (con cargo) y parking exterior (gratuito), ciber corner y guardaesquíes (*El Corte Inglés*, Nieve 2008-2009).

Table 14. Prefixoid *video-* in dictionaries and corpora

Spanish item	DLE 1992	DLE 2001	DLE online	CORDE	CREA	English item	OED	BNC
videocámara	X	✓	✓	X	✓1994	video camera	✓1939	✓1985
videoconferencia	X	✓	✓	X	✓1994	video conference	✓1970	✓1985
vídeo-consola	X	✓	✓	X	✓1995 no hyphen	video game console	✓1976	X
videojuego	X	✓	✓	X	✓1987	video game	✓1973	✓1985

The four examples with *video-* have been incorporated into the current online version of the DLE, when none was present in the first paper version. However, the examples with *video-* were also included in the second paper version of the dictionary. All the items appear in the CREA and none in the CORDE. The four English counterparts are recorded in the OED prior to their appearance in the Spanish sources and three of them are also documented in the BNC. Therefore, the influence of the English language in this word-formation process in European Spanish can be identified through the data provided.

4. Summary and Conclusions

The aim of this article was to demonstrate that the revival of several classic affixes in Spanish is linked to the influence of the English language. In order to test this hypothesis, we have made use of a textual corpus, which stores the information that is obtained from texts written in European Spanish in the 21st century that belong to different genres and formats (both online and printed sources) to extract the lexical elements coined by the word-formation process of affixation, by using prefixes or prefixoids. The value of real data extracted from authentic texts is undeniable, since the samples which are selected are in current use and provide evidence of the productivity of the affixes in contemporary European Spanish.

The examples from the corpus were checked in several lexicographic works and corpora both in Spanish and in English. By consulting five dictionaries and three corpora, we were able to determine whether the items were documented in the English language before their record in the Spanish language. When corroborated, this information provides evidence about the fact that the given Spanish affixes are experiencing a revival thanks to the influence of the English language.

The analysis and interpretation of the data allow for some conclusions to be drawn. Firstly, the use of the prefixes *anti-*, *dis-/de-*, *hiper-*, *inter-*, *mini-*, *multi-* and

ultra- in the examples from the corpus can be ascribed to the influence of the English language when contrasting the timeline in the Spanish and English sources checked. However, the use of *maxi-* and *super-* is not clearly triggered by this influence. Regarding *super-*, nine items coined with this prefix out of eighteen are not recorded in the English language. Similarly, only one derivative with the prefix *maxi-* out of seven items have been found in the English sources. Therefore, the English influence in the word-formation process with these two prefixes cannot be attested. Some combinations, even if they sound plausible in English, are not found in the OED. This could be a clue that they are new formations in Spanish and not properly based on English counterparts. For instance, this is the case of *ultra-diseño*, *ultra lujo* and *ultracorrectora*. Nevertheless, if we take into consideration the data which are presented in our study, it seems clear that the pervasiveness of English is responsible for the expansion of most of the prefixes that were analysed.

Secondly, when looking at the lexical units coined with the prefixoids *agro-*, *ciber-*, *eco-*, *nano-*, *micro-* and *video-*, the relationship between the English and the Spanish word-formation processes seems to be proven. Only two examples out of the twenty-three which were analysed, *ciberregalo* (*cyberpresent/cybergift*) and *ecoagroturismo* (*eco-agrotourism*), are not included in any of the Spanish or English sources used in the study, whereas twenty out of twenty-three are recorded in the OED, always before the incorporation of the items in Spanish. Although these prefixoids have a Latin or Greek origin and do exist in Spanish, there is a tendency to borrow their derivational structure in European Spanish.

Furthermore, different results were found when we checked the items with prefixes and prefixoids in the Spanish sources, mainly in the online version of the DLE and in the CREA corpus. Out of the eighty-five words coined with the prefixes analysed, only 37.6% are recorded in the current online version of the DLE, while 65.9% of those derivatives have been found in the CREA. Regarding the formations with prefixoids, the percentage is similar: out of the twenty-three items, sixteen (69.5%) are included in the CREA and in the online version of the DLE.¹⁶ The difference found between items coined with prefixes and prefixoids could be attributed to the fact that the CREA was continuously updated by including new texts on a regular basis until 2008, so that the contemporary use of the language can be clearly exemplified.

Thirdly, given the peculiarities of some elements which are known as prefixoids, our aim was to show their productivity in Present-Day European Spanish to check whether the neologisms coined through the given prefixoids could have been inspired by their English counterparts, rather than questioning whether they should be categorised as prefixes or compound elements. This is a moot issue, beyond the scope of this study.

Lastly, the English influence is also reflected on the orthography of the neologisms, which are often written with a dash between the prefix or prefixoid and

¹⁶ It should be taken into consideration the fact that the policies for registering words with this type of prefixes in the DLE have changed overtime.

the stem of the word, even though the Royal Academy of the Spanish Language flags this spelling as incorrect and specifically indicates that it should not be used, which is corroborated by other institutions, such as FundéuRAE. Such examples have been found with the prefixes *anti-* (*anti-edad*), *maxi-* (*maxi-brazalete*) and *ultra-* (*ultra-maratón*), and the prefixoids *eco-* (*eco-sostenible*), *micro-* (*micro-inyecciones*) and *video-* (*video-consola*). The Anglicisation process is reflected in the graphical form of the new creations when using the English patterns.

After checking the items extracted from our corpus in several lexicographic sources and in corpora from both the English and the Spanish languages, we can conclude that the results of our analysis point to the influence of the English language on the morphological processes described. Nonetheless, the aim of this paper was to check the connection between English and Spanish. The interaction of Spanish with other Romance languages has not been addressed. This interplay should be explored as a source and possible explanation for the revival of the affixes and affixoids.

References

- Alfaro, Ricardo (1964), *Diccionario de anglicismos*. Madrid: Gredos.
- British National Corpus (BNC), available at: bncweb.lancs.ac.uk/
- Bull, William (1965), *Spanish for teachers: Applied Linguistics*. New York: The Ronald Press.
- Capanaga, Pilar (2002), "Aspectos de la internacionalización del español actual", in San Vicente, Félix (ed.), *L'inglese e le altre lingue europee. Studi sull'interferenza lingüística*. Bologne: Clueb, 67–92.
- Carreras i Goicoechea, María (2002), "Anglicismo y lenguas de especialización: los prefijos de intensificación en italiano, catalán y español", in San Vicente, Félix (ed.), *L'inglese e le altre lingue europee. Studi sull'interferenza lingüística*. Bologne: Clueb, 93–114.
- De la Cruz-Cabanillas, Isabel & Cristina Tejedor-Martínez (2019), "Sport and Adventure Tourism Anglicisms in Spanish: Esferatón or Zorbing?", *Revista Alicantina de Estudios Ingleses*, 32:67–88.
- Dimela, Eleonora & Angela Ralli (2012), "From compounding to prefixation: Diachronic evidence from Modern Greek dialects", in Fábregas, Antonio, Elena Felíu, Josefa Martín & José Pazó (eds.), *Los límites de la morfología. Estudios ofrecidos a Soledad Varela Ortega*. Madrid: Ediciones de la Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, 145–160.
- Estornell-Pons, María (2012), "Novedades léxicas en revistas femeninas: procedimientos de formación y valor semántico-pragmático de las unidades", *Normas. Revista de Estudios Lingüísticos Hispánicos*, 2:77–108.
- Fischer, Roswitha & Hanna Pułaczewska (eds.) (2008), *Anglicisms in Europe: Linguistic Diversity in a Global Context*. Newcastle upon Tyne: Cambridge Scholars.
- FundéuRAE, available at: <https://www.fundeu.es/>

- Furiassi, Cristiano, Virginia Pulcini & Félix Rodríguez-González (eds.) (2012), *The anglicization of European lexis*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Gómez-Capuz, Juan (2004), *Préstamos del español: lengua y sociedad*. Madrid: Arco Libros.
- Gómez-Capuz, Juan (2005), *La inmigración léxica*. Madrid: Arco Libros.
- Görlach, Manfred (2002), *English in Europe*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Gutiérrez-Rodilla, Bertha (1998), *La ciencia empieza en la palabra. Análisis e historia del lenguaje científico*. Barcelona: Península.
- Lang, Mervyn Francis (1990), *Spanish word formation. Productive derivational morphology in the modern lexis*. London: Routledge.
- Lázaro-Carreter, Fernando (1999), "Supertriste". *El dardo en la palabra. El País*, 04/04/1999. Available at:
https://elpais.com/diario/1999/04/04/opinion/923176803_850215.html
- Lorenzo-Criado, Emilio (1996), *Anglicismos hispánicos*. Madrid: Gredos.
- Morin, Regina (2010), "Terminal letters, phonemes, and morphemes in Spanish gender assignment", *Linguistics*, 48(1):143–169.
- Onysko, Alexander (2007), *Anglicisms in German. borrowing, lexical productivity, and written codeswitching*. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter.
- Oxford English Dictionary*, available at: www.oed.com
- Plag, Ingo (2003), *Word formation in English*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Pratt, Chris (1980), *El anglicismo en el español contemporáneo*. Madrid: Gredos.
- Real Academia Española. *Corpus de Referencia del Español Actual (CREA)*. Available at <http://www.rae.es>
- Real Academia Española. *Corpus Diacrónico del Español (CORDE)*. Available at <https://corpus.ra.es/cordenet.html>
- Real Academia Española (1992), *Diccionario de la lengua española*. Madrid: Espasa Calpe. 21st edn.
- Real Academia Española (2001), *Diccionario de la lengua española*. Madrid: Espasa Calpe. 22nd edn.
- Real Academia Española and Asociación de Academias de la Lengua Española (2022), *Diccionario de la lengua española*. Madrid: Espasa Calpe. Available at <http://www.rae.es>
- Real Academia Española and Asociación de Academias de la Lengua Española (2013-), *Diccionario histórico de la lengua española*. Available at <http://web.frl.es/DH>
- Real Academia Española and Asociación de Academias de la Lengua Española (2005), *Diccionario Panhispánico de Dudas*. Madrid: Espasa Calpe. Available at <https://www.rae.es/dpd/>
- Real Academia Española (2009), *Nueva gramática de la lengua española*. Madrid: Espasa Calpe.
- Real Academia Española (2010), *Ortografía de la lengua española*. Available at <http://aplica.rae.es/orweb/cgi-bin/buscar.cgi>

- Sánchez Manzanares, C. (dir.), Azorín Fernández, D., Santamaría Pérez, I. (2016), NEOMA. *Diccionario de neologismos del español actual*. Murcia: Editum. Available at <https://www.um.es/neologismos/index.php/>
- Smead, Robert (2000), "On the assignment of gender to Chicano anglicisms: Processes and results". *Bilingual Review/La Revista Bilingüe*, 25(3):277–297.
- Tejedor-Martínez, Cristina (2017), "The influence of the English language on the description of cosmetic products". *Revista Alicantina de Estudios Ingleses*, 30:303–329.
- Varela-Ortega, Soledad (2005), *Morfología Léxica: La Formación de Palabras*. Madrid: Gredos.
- Varela-Ortega, Soledad & Josefa Martín-García (1999), "La prefijación", in Ignacio Bosque & Violeta Demonte, *Gramática Descriptiva de la lengua española 3. Entre la oración y el discurso. Morfología*. Madrid: Espasa Calpe, 4993–5040.
- Walsh, Andrew Samuel (2017), "Translating false and fickle Anglicisms in modern Spanish". *EPiC Series in Language and Linguistics*, 2:366–373.
- Yañez-López, Faustino Juan (2014), *Prensa y neologismos: la naturaleza adaptativa y creativa del léxico*. Doctoral Thesis. Madrid: UNED.

ANNEX 1. ITEMS WITH PREFIXES IN DICTIONARIES AND CORPORA

Spanish item	DLE 1992	DLE 2001	DLE online	CORDE	CREA	English item	OED	BNC
antialérgico	X	✓	✓	X	✓1997	anti-allergic	X	✓1985
antiarrugas	X	X	✓	X	✓1995	anti-wrinkle	X	✓1960
antibacteriano	X	✓	✓	X	✓1988	anti-bacterial	✓1897	✓1985
anti-colesterol	X	X	X	X	✓1994 no hyphen	anti-cholesterol	X	X
antidepresivo	X	✓	✓	X	✓1987	anti-depressant	✓1962	✓1975
anti-edad	X	X	X	X	✓2001 no hyphen	anti-ageing	X	✓1985
anti-empañamiento	X	X	X	X	X	anti-fog	X	✓1985
antiestrés	X	X	✓	X	✓1986	anti-stress	X	✓1985
antiestresante	X	X	X	X	X	anti-stressing	X	X
antihistamínico	X	✓	✓	✓1969	✓1986	anti-histamine	✓1933	✓1985
anti-polución	X	X	X	X	✓1980 no hyphen	anti-pollution	✓1966	✓1985
antivirus	X	✓	✓	X	✓1993	anti-virus	✓1914	✓1960
desintoxicación	✓	✓	✓	✓1948	✓1989	detoxication	✓1905	✓1985
detoxificación	X	X	X	X	✓1986	detoxification	X	✓1985
detoxificador	X	X	X	X	X	detoxicator	✓1906	X
detoxificante	X	X	X	X	X	detoxifying/ detoxifier	X	✓1985
detoxificar	X	X	X	X	✓1996	detoxify	✓1905	✓1985
distrés	X	X	X	X	✓1986	distress	✓1297	✓1985
hiperactividad	X	✓	✓	✓1912	✓1980	hyperactivity	✓1888	✓1975
hipersensible	✓	✓	✓	✓1919	✓1976	hypersensitive	✓1914	✓1985
hipertensión	✓	✓	✓	✓1912	✓1975	hypertension	✓1939	✓1985
hipertexto	X	✓	✓	X	✓1995	hypertext	✓1965	✓1985
hipervínculo	X	X	✓	X	✓2000	hyperlink	✓1988	X
interactivo	✓	✓	✓	X	✓1992	interactive	✓1972	✓
interconectar	X	✓	✓	X	✓1978	interconnect	✓1865	✓
interconectividad	X	X	X	X	X	interconnectivity	X	✓1985
interconexión	X	✓	✓	✓1957	✓1989	interconnection	✓1856	✓
interfaz	✓	✓	✓	X	✓1992	interface	✓1965	✓
internet	X	X	✓	X	✓1995	internet	✓1974	✓1985
maxi falda	X	X	X	✓1972 unseparated	✓1983 unseparated	maxi-skirt	✓1966	X
maxianillo	X	X	X	X	X	maxi-ring	X	X
maxi-brazaletes	X	X	X	X	X	maxi-bracelet	X	X
maxigargantilla	X	X	X	X	X	maxi-necklace	X	X
maxijersey	X	X	X	X	X	maxi-jumper maxi-sweater	X	X
maxijoyas	X	X	X	X	X	maxi-jewel	X	X
maxiplataformas	X	X	X	X	X	maxi-platform	X	X
minicolección	X	X	X	X	✓2003	minicollection	X	X
minivacaciones	X	X	X	X	✓1985	mini-break	✓1968	✓1985
minifalda	✓	✓	✓	✓1966	✓1988	miniskirt mini-skirt	✓1962	✓1975
minicámara	X	X	X	X	✓1995	minicam	✓1977	X
minilibro	X	X	X	X	X	minibook	X	X
miniserie	X	X	X	X	✓1989	miniseries	✓1963	✓1985
minitallas	X	X	X	X	✓1987	minisizes	X	X
minivestidos	X	X	X	✓1972	✓1991	minidress	✓1965	✓1985
multiactividad	X	X	X	X	X	multi-activity	✓1943	✓1985

multiaventura	X	X	X	X	✓ 2003	multi-adventure	X	X
multicolor	✓	✓	✓	✓1906	✓1987	multicolour	✓1842	✓1985
multicultural	X	✓	✓	X	✓1994	multicultural	✓1935	✓1985
multiculturalidad	X	X	✓	X	✓1994	multiculturalism	✓1957	X
multidisciplinar	X	✓	X	X	✓1996	multidisciplinary	✓1944	✓1985
multifacético	X	X	X	✓1965	✓1977	multifaceted	✓1870	✓1985
multifuncional	X	X	✓	X	✓1975	multifunctional	✓1934	✓1985
multilateral	✓	✓	✓	✓1896	✓1982	multilateral	✓1606	✓1985
multinacional	✓	✓	✓	✓1974	✓1980	multinational	✓1854	✓1985
multisectorial	X	X	X	X	✓1985	multisectoral	✓1953	✓1985
superalimento	X	X	X	X	X	superfood	✓1915	X
superapren dizaje	X	X	X	X	X	superlearning	X	X
superbrillante	X	X	X	X	X	super-smart	✓1870	X
superelegante	X	X	X	X	✓1975	super-smart	✓?1750	X
superespecial	X	X	X	X	✓1994	super-special	X	X
superfeliz	X	X	X	X	✓2001	superhappy	✓	X
superfino	✓	X	X	✓1763	✓1999	superthin	X	X
superguay	X	X	X	X	✓1990	super-cool	✓1915	✓
superhéroe	X	X	✓	X	✓1990	superhero	✓1899	✓
superintensivo	X	X	X	X	X	superintensive	X	✓
supermodelo	X	X	✓	X	✓1977	supermodel	✓1967	✓1985
superper feccionista	X	X	X	X	X	superperfeccionist	X	X
superpoderes	X	X	✓	X	✓1979	superpopular	✓1894	✓
superpopular	X	X	X	X	✓2004	supermodel	X	X
superpro ducción	✓	✓	✓	✓1923	✓1989	superproduction	X	X
superrentable	X	X	X	X	X	superprofitable superworthwhile	X X	X X
supertodo terreno	X	X	X	X	X	super-SUV super 4x4	X	X X
superyate	X	X	X	X	X	superyacht	X	X
ultracorrector	X	X	X	X	X	ultracorrector	X	X
ultradelgado	X	X	X	X	X	ultrathin	✓1949	✓
ultradiseño	X	X	X	X	X	ultradesign	X	X
ultra-dosificado	X	X	X	X	X	ultra-dosified	X	X
ultraligero	✓	✓	✓	X	✓1985	ultralight	✓1974	✓
ultralujo	X	X	X	X	✓2004	ultraluxury	X	X
ultramaratón	X	X	X	X	X	ultra-marathon	✓1977	X
ultrarreparador	X	X	X	X	X	ultrarepairing	X	X
ultrarrealista	X	X	X	X	X	ultrarealist	X	X
ultrarresistente	X	X	X	X	X	ultraresistant	X	X
ultrasonido	✓	✓	✓	✓1957	✓1983	ultrasound	✓1923	✓
ultravioleta	✓	✓	✓	✓1929	✓1975	ultraviolet	✓1840	✓

ANNEX 2. ITEMS WITH PREFIXOIDS IN DICTIONARIES AND CORPORA

Spanish item	DLE 1992	DLE 2001	DLE online	CORD E	CREA	English item	OED	BNC
agroecológico	X	X	✓	X	✓2002	agroecological	✓1940	X
agroturismo	X	X	✓	X	✓1994	agrotourism	✓1987	X
cibercafé	X	X	✓	X	✓1997	cybercafe	✓1994	X
cibercrimen	X	X	X	X	X	cybercrime	✓1991	X
cibercultura	X	X	✓	X	✓1997	cyberculture	✓1963	X
ciberespacio	X	✓	✓	X	✓1995	cyberspace	✓1982	✓1985
cibernauta	X	✓	✓	X	✓1995	cybernaut	✓1965	X
cibernética	X	✓	✓	✓1952	✓1975	cybernetics	✓1948	✓1975
ciberregalo	X	X	X	X	X	cyberpresent cybergift	X	X
ecoagroturismo	X	X	X	X	X	eco-agrotourism	X	X
ecosistema	✓	✓	✓	✓1968	✓1989	ecosystem	✓1935	✓1985
eco-sostenible	X	X	X	X	X	ecosustainable	X	X
ecoturismo	X	✓	✓	X	✓1994	ecotourism	✓1982	✓1985
microcirculación	X	X	X	X	✓1988	micro-circulation	✓1955	✓1985
micro-inyecciones	X	X	X	X	X	micro-jabs micro-injections	✓1921	X
microrelieve	X	X	X	X	X	micro-relief	✓1926	X
nanoestructura	X	X	✓	X	X	nanostucture	✓1978	X
nanotecnología	X	X	✓	X	✓1991	nanotechnology	✓1974	✓1985
nanotubo	X	X	✓	X	✓2003	nanotube	✓1992	✓1985
microcirculación	X	X	X	X	✓1988	micro-circulation	✓1955	✓1985
micro-inyecciones	X	X	X	X	X	micro-jabs micro-injections	✓1921	X
microrelieve	X	X	X	X	X	micro-relief	✓1926	X
nanoestructura	X	X	✓	X	X	nanostucture	✓1978	X
nanotecnología	X	X	✓	X	✓1991	nanotechnology	✓1974	✓1985
nanotubo	X	X	✓	X	✓2003	nanotube	✓1992	✓1985
videocámara	X	✓	✓	X	✓1994	video camera	✓1939	✓1985
videoconferencia	X	✓	✓	X	✓1994	video conference	✓1970	✓1985
video-consola	X	✓	✓	X	✓1995 no hyphen	video game console	✓1976	X
videojuego	X	✓	✓	X	✓1987	video game	✓1973	✓1985